

Synthesis and structural characterization of new [Cu^{II}-TiO₂] composites from Cu^{II}-salen as precursors

Minoru Matsuno^a, Shabana Noor^b, Takashi Numata^a, Tomoyuki Haraguchi^a, Takashiro Akitsu^{*a} and Michikazu Hara^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Tokyo University of Science, Shinjuku-ku, Tokyo, Japan

E-mail : akitsu@rs.kagu.tus.ac.jp

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh-202 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

^cInstitute of Innovative Research, Tokyo Institute of Technology, Yokohama, Kanagawa, Japan

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Abstract : Five salen type copper(II) complexes [CuL¹] (1), [CuL²] (2), [CuL³] (3), [CuL⁴] (4) and [CuL⁵] (5) and their composites with TiO₂, [CuL¹-TiO₂] (6), [CuL²-TiO₂] (7), [CuL³-TiO₂] (8), [CuL⁴-TiO₂] (9) and [CuL⁵-TiO₂] (10) were synthesized and characterized by employing elemental analysis, infra-red (IR) and TD-DFT calculations. The solid state structures of (4) and (5) were confirmed using X-ray diffraction on single crystals. The structural analyses of composites (6-10) along with TiO₂ were performed through X-ray photon spectroscopy (XPS) and powder X-ray diffraction (P-XRD). X-Ray analysis demonstrated that the Cu²⁺ ion in complex (4) acquire distorted square planer geometry and occupy inner chamber (N₂O₂) of the Schiff base ligand whereas in complex (5) two mononuclear units are connected by phenoxo bridge to form a dimer in which Cu²⁺ ions exhibits a five-coordinated square pyramidal coordination geometry. The methoxy groups are free in both complexes. The XPS measurements on composite (9) shows that change of dipole moment due to chemical adsorption, which affect electronic state of TiO₂. The measurement results of P-XRD have been analyzed by employing Rietveld analysis method and a change in volume of TiO₂ for composite (9) is observed.

Keywords : TiO₂, salen-type Cu^{II} complexes, composites, XPS, powder XRD.

Introduction

High energy conversion efficiency have been required for dye sensitized solar cells (DSSC) in practical electricity generation. Ru²⁺ polypyridyl complexes [Ru(dcbpy)₂(NCS)₂]TBA₂, (commercial name N749) had been widely used as dye component. These Ru²⁺-based photosensitizers, with photoelectric conversion to 900 nm exceed 12% efficiency of DSSC. However, the metal is rare and expensive and also susceptible to degradation through dissociation of labile NCS ligands. Successful attempts had been made to increase the stability of dye, by replacing the NCS groups by chelating ligand such as naphthalimide, porphyrin-Zn complexes and phthalocyanine-Cu complexes. Recently, the salen type metal complexes have also proved to be efficient candidates as dyes in DSSC

because the synthesis and chemical modification are easy and the chelate ligands are stable as compared to the existing dyes. They usually show interesting magnetic, optical properties and oxidation-reduction reactivity due to electron transfer. Therefore, this type of complexes is also exploited as catalysts in asymmetric synthesis and redox reactions¹⁻¹². Moreover, salen-type zinc and aluminum complexes increases the power conversion efficiency by substituent effect were also reported in the literature^{13,14}.

In addition, some metal nanoparticle composites exhibit chiroptical properties^{15,16} and chiral catalysis¹⁷, which are formed by addition of chiral additives onto achiral metal nanoparticles. It has been found that the interaction of chiral complexes with nanoparticles give rise to new chiral dichroism (CD)

signal due to dipole interaction and dielectric effect¹⁸. The intensity of induced CD signal may be increase or decrease depends on parallel and perpendicular arrangement of transition moments of metal nanoparticles and chiral additive molecules respectively¹⁹. It has been found that when dyes are absorbed on TiO₂, antibonding orbitals are formed by the overlapping of 2p orbital of oxygen of carboxyl groups with 3d orbitals of Ti. This results in change in electronic states, also changes the adsorption of the composite^{20,21}. In the present article, five Cu^{II}-salen complexes [CuL¹] (1), [CuL²] (2), [CuL³] (3), [CuL⁴] (4) and [CuL⁵] (5) (Scheme 1) and their composites with TiO₂, [CuL¹-TiO₂] (6), [CuL²-TiO₂] (7), [CuL³-TiO₂] (8), [CuL⁴-TiO₂] (9) and [CuL⁵-TiO₂] (10) were synthesized. The Cu^{II}-salen complexes are characterized by elemental analysis, IR and X-ray diffraction analysis on single crystals. The adsorption structures of composites (6-10) were analyzed through SEM, XPS, and powder XRD (P-XRD) measurements.

Experimental

Materials :

Chemicals of the highest commercial grade available, purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, Wako, TCI and

Kanto Chemical were used as received without further purification.

Synthesis of complexes (1-5) :

General procedure for the synthesis of Cu^{II}-salen; CuL¹ (1), CuL² (2), CuL³ (3) and CuL⁴ (4) :

o-Vanillin (0.211 g, 1.0 mmol) was added dropwise to 50 mL methanol solution of (*S*)-1,2-diaminopropane dihydrochloride (0.0737 g, 0.5 mmol) (1), (*1R,2R*)-(-)-1,2-diaminocyclohexane (0.0571 g, 0.5 mmol) (2), (*1R,2R*)-(+)-1,2-diphenylethylenediamine (0.0521 g, 0.5 mmol) (3) and (*R*)-(+)-1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diamine (0.142 g, 0.5 mmol) (4). Then, the resultant mixture was stirred at 313 K for 2 h. Copper(II) acetate monohydrate (0.099 g, 0.5 mmol) was then added, and the solution was further stirred for 2 h. The resulting solution was filtered and placed at room temperature. After a week green crystals of (1-4) were obtained.

CuL¹ (1) :

Yield 0.103 g (50.7%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 724 (s), 851 (m), 879 (m), 1011 (m), 1079 (m), 1099 (m), 1218 (s), 1238 (s), 1308 (w), 1394 (m), 1600 (m), 1629 (s, C=N), 2926 (br, m), 3441 (br, s).

CuL² (2) :

Yield 0.193 g (86.7%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 736 (s),

Scheme 1 Structures of complexes.

851 (m), 978 (m), 1028 (m), 1083 (m), 1224 (s), 1243 (s), 1322 (s), 1350 (m), 1392 (m), 1443 (s), 1473 (s), 1543 (m), 1601 (m), 1628 (s, C=N), 2854 (br, m), 2930 (br, m), 3432 (br, s).

CuL³ (3) :

Yield 0.167 g (61.5%); IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 700 (s), 742 (s), 852 (m), 981 (m), 1000 (m), 1115 (m), 1169 (m), 1220 (s), 1243 (s), 1324 (s), 1393 (m), 1443 (s), 1470 (s), 1542 (s), 1626 (s, C=N), 2831 (br, w), 2928 (br, w), 3053 (w), 3445 (br, s).

CuL⁴ (4) :

Yield 0.181 g (59.0%); Anal. Calcd. for C₃₆H₂₆N₂O₄Cu : C, 65.30; H, 3.96; N, 4.23. Found : C, 64.95; H, 3.58; N, 4.05; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 585 (m), 742 (s), 881 (m), 958 (m), 1067 (s), 1211 (m), 1246 (m), 1363 (m), 1441 (s), 1538 (s), 1610 (s, C=N), 3445 (br, m).

Synthesis of CuL⁵ (5) :

To a solution of 1,2-di(1-naphthyl)-1,2-ethanediamine (0.155 g, 0.5 mmol) dissolved in methanol : CHCl₃ (1 : 1 v/v) (50 ml) was added dropwise *o*-vanillin (0.211 g, 1.0 mmol), and the resultant mixture was stirred at 313 K for 2 h. Copper(II) acetate monohydrate (0.099 g, 0.5 mmol) was then added, and the solution was further stirred for 2 h. Filter the resulting solution and place at room temperature. After 4–5 days, green color crystals appeared.

Yield 0.125 g (39.1%); Anal. Calcd. for C₃₈H₃₀N₂O₄Cu : C, 67.51; H, 4.48; N, 4.11. Found : C, 67.14; H, 4.32; N, 3.88; IR (KBr, cm⁻¹) : 730 (m), 852 (s), 981 (s), 1081 (s), 1168 (s), 1219 (m), 1240 (m), 1321 (w), 1442 (s), 1468 (s), 1542 (s), 1618 (s, C=N), 3431 (br, m).

Preparation of composite of [Cu^{II}-salen-TiO₂](6-10) (powder) :

To a solution of (0.5 mM) (1-5), 0.1 g of TiO₂ particles was added with stirring, and the resulting solution was allowed to stir for another 24 h. Thereafter the powder was filtered and washed with methanol and dried.

Computational methods :

All calculations were performed using the Gaussian 09W Software Revision A.02 (Gaussian, Inc.)²². The gas phase geometry optimizations were carried out using TD-DFT with B3LYP functional. The vertical excitation energy was calculated with the Lanl2dz for Cu with the 6-31+G(d) basis set for H, C, N, O and Cl method based on the singlet ground state geometry.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (C, H and N) were carried out with a Perkin-Elmer 2400II CHNS/O analyzer at the Tokyo University of Science. Infrared spectra were recorded as KBr pellets on a JASCO FT-IR 4200 plus spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹ at 298 K. The powder X-ray diffraction patterns for the complexes of TiO₂ were measured on a Rigaku Smart Lab (CuK α radiation) at 2 θ = 5–60 deg, step width 0.01 deg, scan speed 0.3 deg/min, capillary diameter 0.3 mm. Structural analysis by the Rietveld method²³ was carried out using PDXL2 ver.2.2.1.0 (Rigaku Corporation). XPS was measured on a Shimadzu, ESCA3400 using MgK α source. SEM was measured on a Jeol JSM-7000F.

X-Ray crystallography :

Each single crystal was glued on top of a glass fiber and coated with a thin layer of epoxy resin to measure the diffraction data. Intensity data were collected on a Bruker APEX2 CCD diffractometer with graphite monochromated Mo K α radiation (λ = 0.71073 Å). Data analysis was carried out with a SAINT program package²⁴. The structures were solved by direct methods with a SHELXS-97²⁵ and expanded by Fourier techniques and refined by full-matrix least-squares methods based on F² using the program SHELXL-97²⁶. An empirical absorption correction was applied by a program SADABS²⁶. All non-hydrogen atoms were readily located and refined by anisotropic thermal parameters. All hydrogen atoms were located at geometrically calculated positions and

refined using riding models. Acetate ions may be disordered potentially according to large thermal factors. The formula exhibit solvents of crystal and their occupancy.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and characterization of complexes (1-5) :

The formation of chiral Schiff base ligands has been achieved employing condensation reaction of *o*-vanillin with aromatic diamines in 2 : 1 molar ratio under reflux conditions. The reaction of the condensate with copper acetate afforded in good yields (39–62%) the copper complexes (1-5), which are stable in air and moisture at room temperature. The final products were characterized by elemental analyses and IR. Adsorption of these Cu^{II} complexes (1-5) on TiO₂ resulted in respective composites (6-10).

IR spectral studies of the complexes provided sample information. Observed important IR bands are summarized in the Experimental section. The appearance of a strong band 1610–1629 cm⁻¹ region is characteristic of the coordinated stretching frequency of the iminic bond present in the ligand moiety. These observations support the condensation process followed by the complexation reaction. A medium intensity band at ~980 cm⁻¹ in complex (5) ascertains the formation of a phenoxo (M-O-M) bridge. The appearance of medium intensity band in low frequency region characteristic of $\nu(\text{M-O})$ and $\nu(\text{M-N})$ stretching vibrations were also present in the spectra of the complexes.

The results of the single crystal X-ray analysis of (4) and (5) are summarized in Table 1. A view of the independent molecule of (4) and (5) with labeling of significant atoms is presented in Figs. 2 and 3. Selected bond length and bond angles are given in Table 2. Complexes (4) crystallizes in orthorhombic space group $C222_1$ with $a = 12.8733(14) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 18.8166(14) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 13.5546(12) \text{ \AA}$. The asymmetric

Table 1. Crystallographic data of (4) and (5)

	(4)	(5)
CCDC no.	1536664	1536665
Empirical formula	C ₃₆ H ₂₆ CuN ₂ O ₄ , 0.351(O ₂), O	C ₇₆ H ₆₀ Cu ₂ N ₄ O ₈ , 2(CHCl ₃)
Crystal system	Orthorhombic	Triclinic
Space group	$C222_1$	$P-1$
Z	4	1
a (Å)	12.8733(14)	11.9785(9)
b (Å)	18.8166(14)	12.8155(9)
c (Å)	13.5546(12)	13.1986(10)
α (°)		69.5450(10)
β (°)		83.0200(10)
γ (°)		65.4100(10)
V (Å ³)	3283.4(5)	1725.5(2)
$\rho_{\text{Calcd.}}$ (g/cm ³)	1.298	1.466
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.711	0.910
F(000)	1322.5	782.0
Goodness of fit	1.920	0.909
R_1 [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	0.0776	0.0362
wR_2	0.2375	0.1129

Fig. 2. Molecular structure of (4).

Fig. 3. Molecular structure of (5) showing one of four-coordinated units for clarity.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and bond angles (°)

(4)					
Bond	Distances	Angles			
Cu1-N1	1.970(6)	O1-Cu1-O2	90.7(3)		
Cu1-O1	1.880(5)	O1-Cu1-N1	93.7(3)		
Cu1-N2	1.970(6)	O1-Cu1-N2	149.8(3)		
Cu1-O2	1.880(5)	O2-Cu1-N1	149.8(3)		
		O2-Cu1-N2	93.7(3)		
		N1-Cu1-N2	97.2(3)		
(5)					
Cu1-O1a	1.9077(12)	O1a-Cu1-O2a	89.31(5)	O1a-Cu1-O2b	96.20(5)
Cu1-O2a	1.9090(13)	O1a-Cu1-N1a	92.98(6)	O2a-Cu1-O2b	94.95(5)
Cu1-N1a	1.9347(15)	O2a-Cu1-N1a	176.25(5)	N1a-Cu1-O2b	87.86(6)
Cu1-N2a	1.9568(14)	O1a-Cu1-N2a	176.56(6)	N2a-Cu1-O2b	86.05(6)
Cu1-O2b	2.711(2)	O2a-Cu1-N2a	93.10(6)		
		N1a-Cu1-N2a	84.49(6)		

unit of the complex **(4)** contains independent molecule in which the Cu^{II} ion exhibits a distorted square planer configuration, whereby the dianionic ligands (bina)²⁻ binds in tetradentate fashion via two oxygens and two nitrogens of the Schiff base ligand. The Cu-N1 and Cu-N2 bond lengths are almost equal (about 1.97 Å) but slightly longer than Cu-O1 and Cu-O2 (about 1.88 Å). It may be seen from the Fig. 2 that the two binaphthyl units of the chiral (*R*)-(+)-1,1'-binaphthyl-2,2'-diamine become twisted during complexation reaction of **(4)**. This induces asymmetry in the complex. The methoxy groups are free in the complex.

Complex **(5)** crystallizes in triclinic space group *P*-1 with *a* = 11.9785(9) Å, *b* = 1.8155(9) Å, *c* = 13.1986(10) Å, α = 69.5450(10)°, β = 83.200(10)°, γ = 65.4100(10)°. It consists of two five-coordinated Cu^{II} centers in a square pyramidal coordination geometry formed by two four-coordinated Schiff base ligand units. The basal plane of both copper ions consists of the same tetradentate O₂N₂-donor set of atoms while the apical site is occupied by the phenoxo oxygen atom of another O₂N₂-tetradentate dianion that is basal to the second Cu^{II} metal ion of the dimer. The Cu1-O1' = 2.744(2) Å axial bond length is greater than the equatorial distances (Cu1-O1a = 1.9077(12) Å; Cu1-O2a = 1.9090(3) Å). The diphenyls of the 1,

2-di(1-naphthyl)-1,2-ethanediamine moiety of the ligand (dina)²⁻ are parallel. In addition, a molecule of chloroform is also present in the lattice of the complex.

Table 3. Binding energy of composites **(6-10)** of Ti 2p_{3/2} and dipole moment

Complex	2p _{3/2} (eV)
TiO ₂	459.4
[CuL ¹ -TiO ₂] (6)	459.0
[CuL ² -TiO ₂] (7)	459.2
[CuL ³ -TiO ₂] (8)	459.0
[CuL ⁴ -TiO ₂] (9)	459.3
[CuL ⁵ -TiO ₂] (10)	459.2

TD-DFT calculation was performed on complexes **(1-5)** in order to support assignments of spectra and interpretation of spectral shift. Optimization structure of complex **(4)** is shown in Fig. 4 and electric dipole moment for all the complexes was calculated and summarized as follows : 3.8752 D **(1)** (X, -3.8752); 4.6159 D **(2)** (X, -4.6159); 4.7922 D **(3)** (X, -4.7922); 4.7922 D **(4)** (X, -2.4335); 4.4427 D **(5)** (X, -4.4427). Calculated spectrum and optimized structure for complex **(4)** are shown in Fig. 4.

Structural characterization of composites (6-10) : SEM and XPS :

The morphology and size of the obtained particles

Fig. 4. Calculated CD and UV-Visible spectra of (4) [left up, left down respectively], orbitals of transitions [right up] and dipole moment (violet allow) [right down].

Fig. 5. SEM images of TiO₂ (left) and complex of TiO₂ and composite (9) (right).

have been examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and the images are shown in Fig. 5. For this purpose, TiO₂ and (CuL⁴-TiO₂) (9) were analysed. For TiO₂ only, it can be observed that not all the

Fig. 6. XPS spectra of Ti_{2p} states for the composites (6-10).

particles are spherical, but some of them are irregular. Synthesized composites functionalized with methyl

Table 4. Rietveld analysis parameter for TiO₂ and composites (7, 9 and 10)

Composites	Rwp (%)	Rp (%)	Re (%)	S	χ ²	Maximum shift/e.s.d.
TiO ₂	1.96	1.56	1.07	1.831	3.352	0.000
[CuL ² -TiO ₂] (7)	9.71	6.74	0.80	12.19	148.5	0.102
[CuL ⁴ -TiO ₂] (9)	7.71	4.99	0.84	9.183	84.33	0.046
[CuL ⁵ -TiO ₂](10)	9.14	5.60	0.88	10.34	106.9	0.000

groups are spherical in shape and particle size was found to be 10–20 nm.

The X-ray photon spectroscopy (XPS) spectra of Ti_{2p} states for the composites (6-10) was carried out to analyze the adsorption state of the respective complexes on TiO₂ is shown in Fig. 6. The shift of the peak in the spectra shows the chemisorption of all the complexes (1-5) by methoxy groups in the corresponding composites (6-10). XPS spectra of Ti_{2p} states for the composites (6-10) is shown in Fig. 6. The binding energy and the dipole moments calculated by TD-DFT calculations are summarized in Table 3. It may be concluded from the data that all the composites show no significant change in binding energy when compared with that of TiO₂, but the shift of binding energy is for composite is in order 6=8 > 7=10 > 9 whereas the order of dipole moment is 3 > 2 > 5 > 1 > 4. This change of dipole moment may be due to the chemisorption which affect the electronic state of the TiO₂ in the composites.

Powder-XRD analysis :

P-XRD of the composites (7, 9 and 10) and TiO₂ was measured. The measurement results are shown in the Fig. 7. The measurement results were analyzed by Rietveld analysis method and the results are shown in Fig. 8 and the calculated parameters are summa-

Fig. 7. Powder-XRD spectra of TiO₂ and composite (7, 9 and 10).

Table 5. Structural parameters of composite (TiO₂, 7, 9 and 10)

	TiO ₂		(7)			
	TiO ₂ (Anatase)	TiO ₂ (Rutile)	cyCu (2) Monoclinic (b)	TiO ₂ (Anatase)	TiO ₂ (Rutile)	
Crystal system	Tetragonal	Tetragonal	P12 ₁ /n1, unique-b, cell-2	Tetragonal	Tetragonal	
Space group	I4 ₁ /amd, choice-1	P4 ₂ /mmm		I4 ₁ /amd, choice-1	P4 ₂ /mmm	
a (Å)	3.7838	4.5909	11.8883	3.7926	4.5973	
b (Å)	3.7838	4.5909	9.7533	3.7926	4.5973	
c (Å)	9.5028	2.9569	18.2733	9.5314	2.9596	
α (deg)	90	90	90	90	90	
β (deg)	90	90	100.0767	90	90	
γ (deg)	90	90	90	90	90	
	binaCu (4)	(9)		dinaCu (5)	(10)	
		TiO ₂ (Anatase)	TiO ₂ (Rutile)		TiO ₂ (Anatase)	TiO ₂ (Rutile)
Crystal system	Orthorhombic	Tetragonal	Tetragonal	Triclinic	Tetragonal	Tetragonal
Space group	C222 ₁	I4 ₁ /amd, choice-1	P4 ₂ /mmm	P-1	I4 ₁ /amd, choice-1	P4 ₂ /mmm
a (Å)	12.9924	3.7847	4.5958	11.8138	3.7853	4.7421
b (Å)	18.9058	3.7847	4.5958	12.4702	3.7853	4.7421
c (Å)	13.4449	9.5076	2.9589	12.8844	9.4541	2.9281
α (deg)	90	90	90	70.6186	90	90
β (deg)	90	90	90	82.2581	90	90
γ (deg)	90	90	90	66.7381	90	90

Fig. 8. P-XRD spectra of composite 7, 9 and 10 subjected to separation analysis by Rietveld method.

Fig. 9. Volume of anatase type and rutile type titanium oxide of the composite (TiO₂, 7, 9 and 10).

ized in Table 4.

Separation analysis of titanium oxide was carried out with each composites (6-10), and its volume change was investigated. The results thus obtained are shown in **Fig. 9**. It is evident that, in composite (7) the deposition was increased in both titanium oxide structures. Composite (9) showed almost no volume change. In the case of composite (10), the volume of the anatase type titanium oxide decreases whereas volume of the rutile type titanium oxide increased.

Conclusion

Five new Cu^{II}-salen complexes (1-5) were used as precursors to synthesize five new TiO₂ (6-10) composites. X-Ray analysis on single crystal confirmed that the Cu^(II) in complex (4) acquired square planer geometry whereas in (5), it exhibits square pyramidal geometry. The SEM image confirms that the particle size was in the 10–20 nm. The shift in the peak

of the 2p_{3/2} in XPS spectrum of (6-10) on the 2p orbit of Ti shows that the methoxy group was adsorbed on Ti. The Powder XRD patterns coupled with volume change of titanium oxide for the composite (7) suggest that change in volume contributes to state change due to adsorption.

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Supplementary data

Crystallographic data have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center as CCDC 1536664 and 1536665. These data can be obtained free of charge from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif.

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